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Comparative Study On The Efficacy Of The Synergy Of Three Individual Coccidiocidal Drugs With *Allium sativum* Powder In Broiler Chickens Challenged With *Eimeria tenella* Oocysts

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ABSTRACT

The boom in poultry industry worldwide is confronted by a well-known parasitic disease called ‘Coccidiosis’ resulting to several deaths of poultry and great loses to poultry farmers. The ease of the transmission of these self-limiting parasites in affected farms and the difficulties in the production of reliable coccidiocidal drugs to curtail their excesses have continued to remain a daunting challenge. Here, we describe a possibly more efficacious treatment via synergy of some selected coccidiocidal with bioactive plant (Garlic / *Allium sativum*) suitable for tropical regions. To achieve it, we carefully made a synergy of the *Allium sativum* powder with each of the three selected coccidiocidal/coccidiostatic drugs that are commonly used by poultry farmers. The weight gain/loss, oocysts count, blood parameters and histopathological architecture were investigated in detail. Twenty-two day old broiler chickens of both sexes were randomly assigned to (5) five groups with 15 replicates each. Groups 1- 4 were orally inoculated with 4×10^3 (0.2ml) sporulated oocysts of *Eimeria tenella* as a single gavage, while group 5 (negative control) were administered water. Whereas groups 1-3 were treated with different regimes of drugs, group 4 served as the positive control. The results indicated that inoculation of birds with 4×10^3 sporulated *Eimeria tenella* oocysts significantly reduced growth rate and varied haematological parameters, but increased faecal oocysts shedding with sloughing that caused necrosis in the intestine. These parameters were however reversed after nine days of treatment with significant improvement observed in all the treated groups with the highest effects in groups 1 and 2. Statistical analysis showed a significant difference at $P < 0.05$. In conclusion, we report that the three drugs worked effectively in the boosting of the listed parameters. But importantly, the synergy of Embazin with Garlic Powder was most effective in eliminating oocyst in the faeces, while that of Diclazuril and Garlic Powder had the most improved efficacy on the haematological and histological architectures. We therefore recommend that a combination of the three synthetic drugs with garlic powder could more be suitable for tropical regions.

Keywords: *Eimeria tenella*, drug regimes, weight performance, oocysts count, haematological parameters, histological architecture.

INTRODUCTION

Coccidiosis is a disease of chickens caused by the protozoan parasite of the genus- *Eimeria*. seven species of *Eimeria* have been recognized in chickens, namely; *Eimeria tenella*, *E. acervulina*, *E. brunetti*, *E. maxima*, *E. mitis*, *E. necatrix* and *E. praecox*. [15] of these species, *E. tenella* is one of the most common and pathogenic species that affect the poultry industry, [1] Resulting in 100% morbidity and a high mortality due to extensive damage of the digestive tract.

Coccidiosis is usually established in the intestine, commencing with the invasion of the mucosal epithelium of the intestines by the *Eimeria* sporozoites, leading to inflammation and eliciting of immune response and the production of nitric oxide. the eventual end is reduction in growth of the affected chicken and consequently enormous economic loss. [3] the mechanisms deployed by sporozoites to reach their destination is precisely not known, but it is suggested they must have been transported from the villi within the host lymphocytes particularly the intra-epithelial, [4] cytotoxic t-cells and macrophages. [16-17] With the expansion of poultry farming noting its provision of affordable and high quality proteins, there is the need for an increase surveillance and control of many enteric diseases like coccidiosis which may hamper its boom. [14] Despite progress in the control of coccidiosis to enhance commercial poultry systems, the financial impact of prophylaxis and estimates of production losses due to disease, put the costs of coccidiosis to the poultry industry in Great Britain to at least £38 millions per annum. [18] The quest to comparatively evaluate the efficacy of the synergy of some plants, (*Allium sativum*) with some drugs (Diclazuril, Embarzine forte and Toltrazuril) could be a welcome development since pockets of drug resistant strains especially after prolonged use have been recorded. [11] A large number of anticoccidial drugs are being used for the control of coccidiosis, however, their excessive use has led to the development of drug resistance, residues in the tissues and organs and high economic cost. However, study by Jamil *et al.* (2022), indicated an excellent Oocysts elimination, improved haematological and histological architectures in infected broiler chickens treated with Embazin Forte and Diclazuril respectively, Hence, the need to search and identify more efficacy in the synergy *Allium sativum* with each of the individual drugs (Diclazuril, Embarzine forte and Toltrazuril [DET]) in the tropical climate to mitigate coccidiosis in infected chickens.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area: This research was carried out at both the Poultry house in the department of Animal Science, Federal University Gashua , Yobe State and Parasitology Unit of the National Veterinary Research Institute Vom, Plateau State, Nigeria.

Vaccination of Experimental animals (Birds): one day-old broiler chicken of both sexes were kept at the Poultry house for twenty-two days before the commencement of the study. Within this period, the birds were vaccinated in the first, second and third weeks against common viral diseases like infectious bursal disease (IBD) also known as Gumboro 1, Newcastle Disease (La Sota) 1 and Gumboro 2 on days 7, 14 and 21 respectively using the N.V.R.I Vom vaccination schedule to nullify the possible occurrence of viral infections. The vaccines were administered in their drinking water after about 12hrs of water starvation.

Ethical clearance: All experiments were conducted in accordance with the principles and guidelines for the care and use of laboratory animals. [11]

Innocation of Experimental Animals with Coccidia: On the day 22, the birds were randomly assigned to five (5) groups of 15 replicates and a dose ($4 \times 10^3 = 0.2\text{ml}$) of sporulated oocysts of *Eimeria tenella* was orally given as a single gavage to each bird except the negative control. (i.e, groups 1-4 received same number of oocysts while group 5 (negative control) were not infected but given water through out the experimental period. Nevertheless, group 4 was the positive control (infected but not treated group). Three conventional drugs in synergy with Garlic (*Allium sativum*) Powder, (i.e, Embazin forte + GP, Diclazuril + GP and Toltrazuril + GP) were individually used in a synergistic form to comparatively determine their respective potencies in the treatment of *E. tenella* infection in the broiler

chickens. Three different treatments were administered to groups 1-3, while groups 4 & 5 were left untreated. The groups and their respective treatments are thus;

Group 1 (represents infected and treated with 50% Embazin (E) + 50% Garlic Powder in 4litres of H₂O).

Group 2 (represents infected and treated with 50% Diclazuril (D) + 50% Garlic Powder in 4litres of H₂O).

Group 3 (represents infected and treated with 50% Toltrazuril (T) + 50% Garlic Powder in 4litres of H₂O).

Group 4 (represents infected and non-treated / Positive Control).

Group 5 (represents non-infected and non-treated / Negative Control).

Experimental Design

Parasitological examination (Oocyst Count): collection of faecal samples was done with the aid of a clean hand fitted polythene, labelled with a permanent marker and then taken to parasitology laboratory for evaluation of parasitaemia on day 3 post infection and then subsequent examination after every 3 days for the presence of *Eimeria* oocysts and count per gram (opg) of faeces using the method described by Long and Truiscot; [8] Long and Rowell.[9]

Body weights: weight of each bird was recorded and repeated after every three days until the end of the experiment using the Camry Weighing Scale

Parasitaemia and Haematology: 2ml of blood samples of five birds from each group were randomly collected from their wing veins after the establishment of parasitaemia for haematology. The haematological examination was done to determine the red blood cell counts (RBC), packed cell volume (PCV), neutrophils (NEU), lymphocytes (LYM) and haemoglobin concentration (HBC).

Clinical observations: Treatment commenced on the day 9 post infection following the observations of clinical signs such as bloody diarrhoea, ruffled feathers, loss of appetite, depression, pale combs and establishment of parasitaemia level (90%). Individual's faecal samples (minimum 5 g) were collected after every three days for the entire trial duration, and stored at +4°C until moved to the laboratory for analysis. Visual faecal score was also recorded throughout on the farm, on a scale 0–4, where 0=normal faeces; 1=pasty to semi liquid; 2= liquid; 3= liquid with blood; and 4= liquid with blood and tissue.

Treatments and Histology: The Embazin forte (E) and Garlic powder (GP) were measured using sensitive weighing scale (PB 153 Mettler Toledo weighing scale) and applied in the birds' drinking water. While, Diclazuril (D) and Toltrazuril (T) were measured using 5ml syringe. Both powdered and liquid drugs were applied orally via drinking H₂O. Overall treatment lasted for nine days. There were no signs and symptoms of coccidiosis in negative control (group 5) throughout the experimental period. For histological examination, the experimental birds were randomly selected ten days post treatment for sacrifice by cervical dislocation and for necropsy at the Central Diagnostic Laboratory NVRI, Vom. Their intestines were harvested immediately after the sacrifice.

Statistical Analysis

The data obtained were statistically analysed using SPSS version 20.0. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and comparing groups was performed using the Least Significance Difference (LSD) at $P < 0.05$ as recommended by Petrie and Watson.[13] The criteria used was to measure the degree of coccidial infection, the efficacy of the addition of *A. sativum* to the individual synthetic drugs (i.e, D+GP, E+GP & T+GP) in infected chickens; the mean weight gain in the various groups; the haematological parameters of various groups and the histological analysis of the intestines.

RESULTS

Most of the infected chickens experienced decrease in weight, reduction of appetite, ruffled feathers, diarrhoea and bloody faeces as compared to their control counterparts. However, no mortality was recorded as a result of the parasitaemia prior treatment.

Parasitaemia Evaluation (Oocyst count): Table 1, shows the comparative efficacy of the synergy of individual standard drug with garlic powder on *E. tenella* oocysts in broiler chickens. On day 3, there was shedding of oocysts in all the infected groups (1, 2, 3 & 4) except in the negative control (5) which had

no oocysts output. From day 3 to 6 post infection, there was an increase in the oocysts output across all the infected groups, which insignificantly differed. From day 6 post infection to day 3 post treatment, there was a decrease in oocysts output in all the treatments. After subsequent exposure to the synergy of individual drug with garlic powder (i.e, E+GP, D+GP, T+GP), there was a significant difference (P<0.05) in the effect of the treatments on final oocysts counts on day 9 post treatment. Post hoc test revealed that group 1 [50% (E +GP)], differed significantly from 2 and 3 as it showed most efficacy where no *Eimeria tenella* oocyst was seen in the faeces on day 9 post treatment. Despite there was an abrupt rise in oocysts output in group 3, it had however significantly reduced the anticipated oocysts output if compared to the positive control. Hence, the least effective treatment was in group 3 which had differed significantly with the positive control. There was no oocysts shedding in the negative control throughout the experimental period.

Haematological evaluation: Table 2, shows the comparative efficacy of the synergy of individual drug with garlic powder (E + GP, D +GP, T+GP) on the respective groups (1, 2 and 3) of broiler chicken and their corresponding control groups (4 & 5) pertaining to blood parameters. A significant difference was observed across all haematological parameters post-infection. In packed cell volume (PCV), the highest percentage among the treatments (groups 1, 2 & 3) was observed in group 2; (60mg GP + 50% D) = 27.67 ± 0.58 while the least was observed in group 1; (60mg GP + 50% E) = 26.00 ± 0.58 and they differed significantly post-infection. For red blood cell count (RBC), significant difference was observed among the treatments, with group 1 (60mg GP + 50% E) having the highest RBC count = 2.03 ± 0.03 . The haemoglobin concentration post treatment in group 2; (60mg GP +50% D) = 9.10 ± 0.06 also differed significantly from others by having the highest concentration.

Table 1: Comparative Efficacy of the synergy of individual standard drug with garlic on *E. tenella* oocysts counts (Parasitaemia level) in Broiler chickens

Group	Treatment	Post infection		Post treatment		
		egg counts on day 3	egg counts on day 6	egg counts on day 3	egg counts on day 6	egg counts on day 9
1	50% E+ 60mgGP	3.00 ^{abc} ± 0.00	21.00± 4.58	46.67± 19.65	2.33 ^a ± 0.33	0.00 ^a ± 0.00
2	50% D + 60mgGP	4.00 ^{abc} ± 1.00	46.67± 14.53	10.67± 7.22	4.33 ^a ± 0.89	9.00 ^b ± 0.58
3	60mg GP + 50% T	1.00 ^a ± 0.00	15.00± 2.89	8.33± 3.33	3.0 ^a ± 0.58	29.00 ^c ± 2.08
4	Positive control	4.00 ^{ab} ± 1.53	30.00± 7.64	68.33± 9.28	166.67 ^b ± 44.10	167.68 ^c ± 43.20
5	Negative control	0.00 ^a ± 0.00	0.00± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ^a ± 0.00	0.00 ^a ± 0.00
			NS	NS	0.00	0.00

NS- No significant difference, E- Embazin, D- Declazuril, T- Toltrazuril , entries with same superscripts on the same columns share no significant difference, Critical P value-0.05

On the effects of the various Treatments on Weight of the Broiler Chickens, from day 3 to 9 pre-inoculation, there was a significant weight gain across all the treated groups and their controls. On day 3 post-inoculation, there was a significant difference in the mean weight loss across all the infected groups. However, on days 6 to 9, there was no significant difference in weight gain or loss in all the infected groups as compared to their negative control. From days 3 to 6 post treatment, there was a significant difference in weight gain in the treated groups. Group 3 was statistically same as the negative control

(group 5) as weight gain was observed in this group (negative control) through out the experimental period.

Histopathology

At the time of collection, all the birds groups had coccidiosis and were recovering except the negative control group which were neither infected nor treated. The intestinal epithelial cells of most of the infected groups were sloughed and depleted as a result of invasion by the oocysts of *Eimeria* spp. The caecum had a sloughing of the epithelia and clusters of oocysts invading the villi and consequently affect the blood capillaries beneath the villi, resulting to leakage of blood into the intestine, hence, the presence of blood in the faeces. However, most of the caecal portions especially in the negative control (group 5), were intact with short & broad villi and no pathology observed. In the duodenum, clusters of oocysts along with duodenal debris were seen, and there was sloughing of the intestinal epithelia due to invasion of the merozoites.

The absence of oocysts in the intestine despite the sloughing of the intestine is attributed to healing process (occurrence of recovery). It was carefully and clearly observed that the treated groups showed some level of interventions compared to the positive control (group 4/ infected but not treated) which had clusters of oocysts along with epithelial debris, lymph node in the outer longitudinal muscle and infiltration of the caecum which is an indication of infection.

Treatment	Small Intestine	Large Intestine	
Various Drugs	Duodenum	Ileum	Caecum
Embazin + Garlic: No oocyst infection recorded			
	Plate 2: Duodenum with severe sloughing and depletion of epithelia. H & E Stain x100		
	Plate 1: Caecum with severe sloughing and depletion of epithelia. H & E Stain x100		
Diclazuril + Garlic: No oocyst infection recorded			
	Plate 5: Duodenum with sloughing of the intestinal epithelia due to invasion of merozoites. H & E Stain x100		
	Plate 3: Caecum with clusters of oocysts and epithelial debris. H & E Stain x400		
	Plate 4: Caecum with sloughing of the intestinal epithelia and clusters of oocysts mingled with debris. H & E Stain x100		
Toltrazuril + Garlic No oocyst infection recorded			
	Plate 6: Caecum with characteristic short and broad villi. No pathology observed. H & E Stain x400		
	Plate 7: Duodenum with clusters of oocysts in intestinal epithelia and epithelial debris. H & E Stain x 40.		

DISCUSSION

The severity of *Eimeria* infection in chickens has been characterized by loss of body weight, excretion of faecal oocysts, and the presence of intestinal lesions (Idris et al., 1997). A study by Jamilu et al., 2022, revealed that the average potency of each of the standard drugs (E, D, T) induced anticoccidial/coccidiostatic effect against *Eimeria tenella*. However, this study on the synergy of these drugs with *Allium sativum* showed more efficacy on the devastating effects of coccidiosis on clinical signs of birds ranging from reduction in weight gain, sloughing of intestinal epithelia and necrosis leading to reduction in the concentration of red blood cells. Herein, the number of oocysts recorded in all the groups post treatment significantly reduced compared to the infected but not treated control group 4, which had the highest oocysts count. Large number of oocysts was produced in all the infected groups prior treatment. With the commencement of various treatments, there was a significant reduction in the total oocysts output on day 9 post treatment especially in the group treated with Embazin and Garlic powder.

By this, it can be concluded that synergy of Embazin with *Allium sativum* powder has most effect on *E. tenella* oocysts than the synergies of Diclazuril with *Allium sativum* powder & Toltrazuril with *Allium sativum* powder.

In the blood parameters, it was observed that there was a significant reduction in the packed cell volume, haemoglobin concentration and red blood cell counts post infection. This result agrees with Witlock (1983), who observed a significant decrease in red blood cells, haemoglobin concentration and packed cell volume of *E. tenella* infected chickens and suggested that the decline may be due to the severe bleeding and tissue damage in the mucosa of duodenum originated from invasion of *E. tenella*.

An increase in the lymphocyte and white blood cell counts was also recorded among the infected groups of birds. These parameters changed significantly post treatment with increase in the red blood cells count and haemoglobin concentration. There was also a reduction in lymphocyte counts after treatment. The RBC counts & percentage of PCV were highest in group 2 (50% Diclazuril + 50% G.P) post treatment.

The results also revealed increase in weight gain of infected and treated birds as compared to the positive control (infected but non-treated group) and negative control (non-infected, non-treated group) which had the lowest and highest body weight gain post treatment respectively. This agrees with the findings by (Chapman, 1998; Lillehoj & Lillehoj, 2000; Guo et al., 2007). The photomicrograph of the intestines showed varying degrees of epithelial sloughing and depletion which was as a result of the parasitic infection by *E. tenella* and evidently seen in the varying stages of their developmental stages. This is in synchrony with studies by Maskerem et al. (2013) who observed excessive tissue damage, haemorrhage, presence of clusters of large schizonts and merozoites in the caeca of birds infected with *E. tenella* & *E. brunette*. Due to the various treatments administered to the birds, there was a moderate sloughing and degeneration of intestinal epithelial lining in group 3. Obviously, group 2 had the best architecture of intestinal epithelial lining compared to other groups. Group 4 had a severe destruction of its intestinal crypts due to lack of intervention.

CONCLUSION

With the evaluation of the effects individual drugs in synergy with *Allium sativum*, we were able to further ascertain the anticoccidial activities of these drugs against *E. tenella* as evident from reduction with even elimination of oocysts in the faeces, improvement in weight gain, haematological parameters and recovering of intestinal architecture after distortion via sloughing due to the infection (coccidiosis). The severity of coccidiosis observed based on the oocysts counts, haematology, histopathology and weight gain was high, therefore, the disease caused by *E. tenella* if untreated has a destructive effect on broiler chickens. The untreated group (group 4) of the birds had the lowest parameters with increased oocyst number, distorted intestinal architecture which is an indication of the efficacy of the various treatments.

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Authors Contribution

MJA: literature search, clinical studies, experimental studies, data acquisition and manuscript preparation. MJA: concept, design, definition of intellectual content, literature search, clinical studies, experimental studies, data acquisition, data analysis, statistical analysis, manuscript preparation, manuscript editing and manuscript review. MJA: clinical studies, experimental studies, data acquisition. MJA: clinical studies, experimental studies, data acquisition. MJA: clinical studies, experimental studies, data acquisition. DA: clinical studies, experimental studies, data acquisition. MJA: clinical studies, experimental studies, data acquisition. ONG: clinical studies, experimental studies, data acquisition. MJA: clinical studies, experimental studies, data acquisition. DA: clinical studies, experimental studies, data acquisition. SAB: clinical studies, experimental studies, data acquisition. DA: clinical studies, experimental studies, data acquisition. SAB: clinical studies, experimental studies, data acquisition. MJA: manuscript preparation, manuscript editing and manuscript review. MJA: data analysis, statistical analysis, manuscript preparation, manuscript editing and manuscript review. ONG: data analysis, statistical analysis manuscript preparation, manuscript editing and manuscript review.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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